

Management of vitamin D toxicity: Successful healing treatment of a 69 years old female patient using Yoga Prana Vidya Protocols

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Abstract

Introduction: The occurrence of toxicity or poison effects of excessive use of unsupervised Vitamin D supplements, though it is rare, is a well-researched topic. The health effects can be serious if it is not promptly identified and acted upon. This paper presents a case of 69 years old female patient suffered debilitating effects of Vitamin D Toxicity through self-medication, who was treated with Yoga Prana Vidya System by a team of two healers successfully.

Method: This paper uses case study method of collecting data from patient records, healers' records and patient feedback through her family.

Results: Within 10 days of YPV healing, the bedridden patient regained strength progressively and was able to rise up and walk with support. After the next 4 weeks of YPV healing support she was able to do household chores and walk longer. After next four months, her blood tests showed normal levels of Vitamin D.

Conclusions: Health care providers should monitor use of these supplements, especially in the population at risk due to high dose requirements. Yoga Prana Vidya system of healing offers support system needed in the management of excessive use of Vitamin D supplements, rehabilitating the patients holistically as is observed in this case study. Further research on this topic is recommended.

Keywords: Vitamin D Toxicity (VDT); Vitamin supplement overuse; Yoga Prana Vidya System ®; YPV®

1. Introduction

1.1. Vitamin D toxicity

Vitamin D is both a nutrient we eat and a hormone our bodies make. It is a fat-soluble vitamin that has long been known to help the body absorb and retain calcium and phosphorus; both are critical for building bone. Also, laboratory studies show that vitamin D can reduce cancer cell growth, help control infections and reduce inflammation. Many of the body's organs and tissues have receptors for vitamin D, which suggest important roles beyond bone health, and scientists are actively investigating other possible functions.[1]

Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin that is found in some animal food products and is also synthesized in the human body by exposure to the sun. Toxicity of vitamin D leads to hypercalcemia and imbalance in the regulation of bone metabolism; the resultant hypercalcemia leads to clinical manifestations and symptoms of toxicity. [2]

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As a consequence of hypercalcemia the clinical manifestations of VDT include gastrointestinal symptoms (constipation, nausea, vomiting), fatigue, anorexia, polyuria/polydipsia, dehydration, and neurological manifestations (difficulty in concentration, irritability, drowsiness and coma). One study found that the most common clinical manifestation in sample patients was gastrointestinal symptoms (93.7%) followed by polyuria/polydipsia (46.8%) and neurological manifestations (37.5%). [3]

A study by Parjeet Kaur et al. (2015) revealed that irrational use of vitamin D in mega-doses resulted in VDT in all cases they investigated. Awareness among healthcare providers regarding the toxic potential of high doses of vitamin D and cautious use of vitamin D supplements is the key to prevent this condition. [4] Clinical management of vitamin D toxicity (VDT) is mainly supportive and focuses on lowering the levels of calcium.

1.2. Yoga Prana Vidya System

Yoga prana vidya system of healing has been successfully applied to a wide range of illness conditions as complementary and as also as an alternative medicine, as is evident from over 70 published research papers. YPV is an integrated and holistic system, which consists of physical and breathing exercises, meditation techniques, and bioplasmic (Pranic) energy healing techniques.

Literature shows published successful case reports on applications of YPV include, treatment of difficult medical cases, diabetes management and control, removing arterial block in heart without surgery, vision improvements for participants of an eye camp, improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme, Role of YPV in first aid and emergency, speedy recovery of COVID patients, treatment of hypothyroidism, lowering academic anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children, saving life of a snake-bitten human female, managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy, healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation, treatment and cure of PCOS condition, a case of breast cancer successfully treated, de-addiction cases, etc.[5-19]

A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners, significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees, and improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children, and effects of a month YPV residential programme.[20-23]

Here we present a case report of Vitamin D overuse by a female aged 69 years due to a lack of awareness and self-medication that led to complications, saved however through A YPV intervention conducted by two YPV healers using distal mode of healing techniques.

2. Case report

2.1. Patient details

Patient was a female aged 69 years living with husband and children at the time of this episode.

2.2. Health condition before YPV healing

On 20 June 2022, the patient experienced a lot of pain in knee joints. Suspecting it to be vitamin D deficiency as it happened earlier, she took 10 sachets of Vitamin D 6000iu each for 6 days between 20th June and 26th June. She fell sick, was bed ridden, experiencing severe weakness, heaviness, giddiness, nausea and vomiting sensation. She was lying down on bed most of the time being unable to get up.

On 27th June 2022 she contacted one YPV healer (Healer 2) who is also a Homoeopathy lady doctor from whom she used to take homeopathic medicines earlier for many years whenever she had any health issues. This Homoeopathy doctor was also an associate certified YPV healer. The Healer 1 asked for details of symptoms and asked the patient to get her Vitamin D test done, suspecting it to be Vitamin D toxicity. Patient was too weak and unable to sit, hence didn't get the test done. When Healer 2 insisted on to visit a doctor and get physical check-up done, she went to a doctor around 2nd week of July 2022.

2.3. YPV Healing intervention & results

Then Healer 2 contacted on 28th June another Healer (Healer 1) who is a certified YPV Healer and pursuing 1 year program in YPV ashram and informed patient details, and they both started healing the patient. No medicines were

administered to the patient while conducting YPV healing sessions. She stated doing Rhythmic Yogic Breathing four times daily and Forgiveness Sadhana once daily using YPV Sadhana app as guided by Healer 2.

The healers found her solar, navel, and basic chakras slightly overactive and highly congested. Her upper chakras, i.e., ajna, crown, throat were too big and highly congested. Even front heart chakra and back heart chakra were found congested. Mengmein Chakra was overactive and congested. Front spleen and back spleen were slightly congested. All upper major chakras were also highly congested and also energy of her eyes. Patient had earlier tinnitus that also surfaced now post this episode.

Using HDP level 1 protocol, healing was done with thorough blood cleansing, internal organ cleansing and healing with blue tube technique for ears was done, and miraculous healing was used on limbs. Thorough cleaning was done for liver, kidneys and all joints, and also heart healing protocol was done.

Within 3 days, i.e., by 1st July, her nausea feeling diminished.

She visited a doctor locally in her town on 2nd July. On doctor's advice, physiotherapy treatment for spine started. In another 3 days, i.e., by 4th July she was able to get up from bed.

There was still too much of weakness. After next 4 days of healing, i.e., by 8th July she was able to walk with support and eat little food. Her joints of legs, hands and even spine had pain. She also had giddiness, though somewhat reduced.

After next 10 days, i.e., by 18th July she was able to walk. Giddiness got eliminated. Most of her pains reduced. She resumed her day-to-day work from 22nd July. Still, she complained of muscle weakness, knee pain and backpain while doing light domestic work. Healings were continued for her.

After the next 4 weeks of YPV healing support, i.e., by 15th August, she was able to cook full meal and walk around the apartment blocks about half a Kilometre. Earlier she used to walk 2 to 3 kms. After doing morning household work she was experiencing weakness, but the patient found some relief with breathing exercises. Gradually, weakness also reduced and she was able to walk longer. Still, she felt slight heaviness in joints for which healings continued for her and her body pain reduced, her normal walk started and her other routine activities were normalized.

After repeated requests from the healers, the patient finally got blood test done on **5th September 2022** and still the vitamin D levels were found higher than normal (149.5 ng/ml against maximum allowed 100 ng/ml). Doctor observed that, though the Vitamin D levels were higher than normal, the patient's general condition was much better by then, and did not prescribe any further medications.

Healer 1 observed that though the patient took many sachets of Vitamin D supplement, she had by now comparatively lesser issues, and requested to get Vitamin D test done. But according to the patient, pains in her limbs remained as they were before she took vitamin D sachets, hence the healers continued healing sessions up to 20th September, till her remaining pains also reduced gradually. She further continued to do Rhythmic Yogic Breathing and Forgiveness Sadhana.

Due to a follow up by the healers after further 4 months, the patient's blood tests were conducted on 19 January 2023 that showed acceptable Vitamin D levels of 64.8 (reference of sufficiency is <100ng/ml, and toxicity is >100 ng/ml). She also reported that her tinnitus pain also considerably reduced.

3. Discussion

The occurrence of VDT, though it is rare, is a well-researched topic in medical science. The health effects can be serious if it is not promptly identified and acted upon. Increased public awareness of vitamin D-related health benefits have a tendency to increase the risk of VDT due to self-administration (without medical supervision) of vitamin D in doses higher than recommended for age and body weight or even higher than the established upper limit intake values. Treatment of VDT consists of first- and the second-line treatment strategies in main stream medicine. [24] Clinical management of vitamin D toxicity is mainly supportive and focuses on lowering the levels of calcium.[25]

4. Conclusion

Patient education regarding the harmful effects of overuse of vitamin D supplements is extremely important. Patients should be educated on adhering to the prescription regimen, especially those who are on high doses of vitamin D for the treatment of underlying medical conditions. They should also be made aware of the importance of follow up while being on high dose supplements to avoid the risk of vitamin D toxicity. Vitamin D is widely prescribed and is also used as over-the-counter formulation by patients. Health care providers should monitor closely use of these supplements, especially in the population at risk due to high dose requirements. Yoga Prana Vidya healing techniques offer support system needed without the use of any drugs and is entirely safe to normalise the patient with holistic benefits.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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